

Synergy and Integration as a Strategy for Strengthening the Role of Libraries Through Program “UGM Library Serves”

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Abstract—The low level of public interest in reading and the low level of social welfare require the role of government and social institutions to be further improved. Libraries as institutions that operate in the field of education play a very important role in overcoming these problems. Synergy and integration need to be carried out by libraries with other units to increase their role, function and position as sources of information, agents of change for the development of science and technology. With the "UGM Library Serves" program, namely Inspiration Classes and Optimizing Community Reading Parks (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat), it is hoped that it will be able to stimulate and ground the Indonesian National Reading Movement, to increase the intelligence and welfare of society. UGM can contribute to efforts to improve the quality of the nation by increasing high interest in reading, the nation will be able to achieve progress and have a competitive advantage.

Keywords— Integration; library role; library service; synergy.

I. INTRODUCTION

A great nation is a nation that continues to build and develop its civilization through education. The development and development of education in terms of various aspects such as education from an early age to higher level education, formal and informal education is a reflection of the nation's efforts to carve out progress in civilization through education as its main instrument. (<http://pustaka.pu.go.id>). According to UNESCO, in 2012, the reading interest index in Indonesia had only reached 0.001. This means that for every 1,000 people, there is only one person who has an interest in reading (https://www.kominfo.go.id/content/detail/10862/teknologi-masyarakat-indonesia-malas-baca-tapi-cerewet-di-medsos/0/sorotan_media). Meanwhile, the UNDP released that the literacy rate for Indonesian adults is only 65.5%, while Malaysia has reached 86.4%. (<https://jatim.antaranews.com/berita/177655/apa-kabar-minat-baca-Rakyat-Indonesia>). According to the 2019 PISA Program of International Student Assessment (PISA), it is stated that the level of public interest in reading in Indonesia is 62 out of 70 countries surveyed. Although according to the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) 2021, Yogyakarta people's interest in reading is at level 70.55, the highest in all of Indonesia (<https://databoks.katadata.co.id/datapublish/2022/03/02/warga-yogyakarta-paling-gemar-membaca-se-indonesia>).

Apart from people's interest in reading which is considered to be still low, the problem currently being faced is the influence of gadgets which are not good for the development of our students and are increasingly distancing children from the culture of reading. With the above conditions, what efforts need to be made to improve people's interest in reading, increase awareness of the importance of science and technology, and this will automatically improve the welfare of the Indonesian people and especially the people of Yogyakarta.

II. THEORETICAL BASIS

Definition of Synergy and Integration

Synergy

Synergy (Synergy) is a form of win-win cooperation that is produced through collaboration between each party without any feeling of defeat. Synergy /si·ner·gi//synergies/n 1 joint activities or operations; 2. synergism; synergize /ber·si·ner·gi/incarry out joint activities or operations, mengnyinergikan /mangnyinergi can/ininvigorate (<http://id.wikipedia.org>). According to Stephen Covey in his book *Habits of Highly Effective People*, if $1 + 1 = 3$, then that's it which are called "Synergy". Synergy is complementing and complementing differences to achieve results greater than the sum of the parts. The concept of synergy is result-oriented and positive, diverse perspectives replace or complement paradigms, mutual cooperation and the same goal and there is agreement, it is very effectively pursued and is a process.

Through synergy, cooperation from different paradigms will create greater and more effective results in connection with the process undertaken showing the same goals and agreement for positive results. Examples that we often see of the synergy concept are:

$$1 + 1 = 3 \rightarrow \text{Synergy}$$

$$1 + 1 = 1 \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \text{Compromise}$$

$$1 + 1 = < 1 \rightarrow \text{Negative Synergy (Anergy)}$$

Synergizing means respecting each other's differences in ideas, opinions and being willing to share them. Synergizing is not selfish, but thinks win-win and no party is harmed or feels disadvantaged. Synergy aims to combine separate parts.

<http://ikhtisar.com/sinergi-sebagai-bentuk-kerjasama-kreatif>

The picture above shows that working together and uniting will produce satisfactory results compared to working individually.

Integration

Integration comes from English "*integration*" which means perfection or whole. *integration* /in·teg·ra·si/n blending until it becomes a complete or rounded unity; *integrated* in unite (join to become a whole); *integrate* in combine; unite. The driving factors in integration are internal factors including self-awareness as a social creature, demanding needs, spirit and spirit of mutual cooperation; and external factors, namely the demands of contemporary developments, cultural similarities, open opportunities to participate in life together, the same vision, mission and goals; tolerance attitude; the existence of a value consensus; there are challenges from outside the group homogeneity factor. (<http://id.wikipedia.org/>)

Library

The development and development of education as an effort to carve out civilization must always be supported by facilities and infrastructure, which are able to support the existence of that education. One of the fundamental instruments that must be managed well in order to realize educational goals is the construction and development of libraries as institutions that manage collections of written works, printed works, recorded works in order to meet the strategic needs of education, research, preservation and recreation in educating the nation's life. (anonymous, tt)

According to Library Law no. 43 of 2007, it is explained that libraries area institution that manages collections of written works, printed works and/or recorded works professionally with a standard system to meet the educational, research, preservation, information and recreation needs of users. So, the definition of a library is that it is (1) a collection of library material books, (2) managed professionally with a certain system, (3) managed by institutions or institutions and/or individuals, (4) organized for the needs of users. (Saleh, 2011: 3 -4).

Libraries are a means of disseminating information,

science and technology and a source of information for everyone. For this reason, the services provided are user-oriented *user education* so that it can support the empowerment of the Indonesian people to become an intelligent nation that always wants to progress. Active role from all levels of society to achieve the nation's ideals. Libraries can also provide guidance so that people become more aware that reading culture is important for developing skills at work and for increasing mastery of science and technology. To support the role of the library as a center for lifelong education, the library can collect reading materials that are directed towards the application of appropriate technology. So that people can develop their abilities and knowledge which can be used as added value to their quality of life. Libraries can act as a liaison between appropriate technology experts and the user community who need technical guidance. (Saleh, 2011:11-13)

Higher Education Libraries are institutions that manage collections of written works, printed works, and/or recorded works professionally with a standard system to meet the educational, research, preservation, information and recreation needs of users. The University Library functions as a source of learning, research, internal deposit, preservation and networking center for the academic community in the tertiary environment (Saleh, 2011: 45-46). Higher Education Libraries have duties and functions to support the implementation of the Higher Education Tri Dharma of research, teaching and community service.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Library Synergy and Integration

Synergy and integration are words we are familiar with, togetherness, a sense of mutual belonging, a sense of helping each other, a sense of progress are steps that can be taken. In synergy theory, $1 + 1$ is not 2 but rather, $1 + 1 > 2$, that is an expression that can be conveyed that synergy and integration are very important as a form of mutually beneficial cooperation.

Synergy and integration are steps taken by libraries to increase their role and existence as sources and providers of information. As an information provider institution that collects, collects, processes, presents and disseminates information to the public in order to make the life of the nation and state smarter.

The library does not belong to us alone, but the library belongs to the community. Libraries cannot stand alone but must collaborate and unite with other libraries and other units. To be able to provide maximum functions and benefits to the community, libraries must be able to collaborate and unite with other parties.

As an example of synergy and integration that has been carried out by several libraries, for example:

1. The National Library collaborates with artists by creating various advertisements, for example with public figures in Indonesia Tantowi Yahya, Jaja Miharja, Rieke Diah Pitaloka, Marshanda, Kiwil, Tukul and others. In this advertisement, the National Library created the motto Library, with the aim of making people aware of the importance of reading and the

importance of libraries.

- "The Library Law guarantees that people will be smart", - "Libraries: Smart Tools for Smart People";
- "Read? Remember the Library!"

2. Regional Library with Jogja Library for All, Taman Pintar (Smart Park), "Taman Bacaan Masyarakat" Community Reading Park (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat), Reading Interest Popularization Movement (GPMB)

3. UGM Library with the Gajah Mada Library Fair (GMLF) which collaborates with Private Companies, Publishers, ICT Groups, Regional Libraries, Distributors. Apart from that, integrating systems, services and management with units in the faculty, book reviews, training for human resources and many other collaborations are carried out. All this is done as a strategy to strengthen the role of libraries.

4. School Libraries by collaborating with the ATPUSI organization (Indonesian School Library Staff Association)

5. Higher Education Libraries with their organizations in FPPTI (Indonesian Higher Education Library Forum),

6. DIKTI with the INHERENT (Indonesian Higher Education Network) program, is one of the programs to improve the quality of education. This technology has been spread to 32 points throughout Indonesia and Gajah Mada University is one of the points to provide access services around the Yogyakarta and Solo areas.

7. SLIMS (Senayan Library Management System), collaboration in the IT sector in libraries

8. In general, there are many organizations and activities in the library sector as a strategy to strengthen the role of libraries at national and international levels, for example the existence of IFLA (The International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions), CONSAL (Congress of Southeast Asian Librarians), FPPTI (Forum of University Libraries Indonesian Higher Education), IPI (Indonesian Librarian Association), KPDI (Indonesian Digital Library Conference), International Association of School Librarianship (IASL), The Conference of Directors of National Libraries in Asia and Oceania (CDNLAO), Indonesian National Reading Movement (GNIM), Garuda Portal (Indonesian Digital Referral Platform) and others

Program "Gajah Mada University Library Serves". The "UGM Libraries Serve" program is one of the steps taken as a strategy to strengthen the role of libraries. To carry out the duties and functions of the library in supporting the implementation of the Tri Dharma of Higher Education, especially in the field of community service, the "UGM Library Serves" will provide considerable benefits for rural communities, especially in remote areas. Considering that UGM is *university of the people*. The Chancellor of UGM stated "In the past, UGM was formed by the Indonesian people for the Indonesian people. Currently, one of UGM's superior programs is community service and empowering the UGM community through Real Work Lectures (KKN). The service carried out by UGM through UGM KKN begins with sending auxiliary teachers to areas in need with the aim of solving various national problems such as health, disasters, renewable energy, etc.," (ugm.ac.id).

To support the implementation of UGM's flagship program in community service and empowerment, two activities of the "UGM Library Serves" Program are:

1. Inspiration Class
2. Community Reading Parks (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat): Optimizing existing TBMs and building TBMs in areas that don't have any

1. Inspiration Class

Inspiration Class is an effort to close the distance between the educated middle class and the educational realities of economically weaker sections of society. The Inspiration Class is a forum to invite all parties to build Indonesian education. (Anies Baswedan, 2013). The Inspiration Class was carried out by holding a roadshow to elementary schools in Yogyakarta, which involved all librarians at UGM to join in to make the program to make the lives of people in rural areas a success.

Elementary schools are the targets of this program. A wise saying states that "*If you want to create change, start with the children*". Therefore, the targets for implementing this Inspiration Class are elementary schools in Yogyakarta, especially in remote areas. This Incipation Class instills that every action, idea, work is a seed of inspiration for children, which will continue to grow even after they are gone. The initial steps that need to be taken are:

1. Collect data/inventory of elementary schools in remote areas, for example in the Merapi slopes, rural Bantul, Wates which are far from urban areas.
2. Submit an application to the school where the Inspiration Class is to be held
3. Coordinate librarians to be involved
4. Provide training to librarians
5. Librarians are distributed to designated areas
6. Librarians are tasked with instilling enthusiasm and motivating and raising awareness of the importance of education, science and technology.
7. Librarians encourage children to dream and aspire high for a bright future as the nation's next generation

This activity takes the form of:

- Teaching for a day, providing motivation and inspiration by arousing enthusiasm for the importance of education, the importance of reading, the importance of science, technology, science and religion so that children can excel in achievement, have good personality and be religious.

With the Inspiration Class, it is hoped that elementary school children will develop high dreams and aspirations, becoming successful children in the future because they have awakened awareness of the importance of education to educate themselves and improve the welfare of their lives.

2. Community Reading Park (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat)

Community reading parks (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat) are places to serve the interests of residents living in the surrounding area. Consisting of all levels of society without distinguishing between social, economic, cultural, religious, customs, level of education, age and so on. According to Sutarno NS (2006: 19) in (<https://id-id.facebook.com/FungsiTaman/posts/316742508442307>)

Community Reading Parks (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat) have

the responsibility, authority and rights of the local community in building, managing and developing them. In this case, it is necessary to develop a sense of belonging (*sense of belonging*), take responsibility (*sense of responsibility*) and take care of (*join hangrukebi*). (<https://id.id.facebook.com/FungsiTaman/posts/316742508442307>)

Figure 1. Taman Bacaan Masyarakat Sakinah, Wates Kulonprogo, Uogyakarta, Indonesia

Organizing Community Reading Parks (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat) as a place to provide reading materials in order to help and provide services to the community in accordance with the needs, literacy abilities and reading skills of the community evenly, widely, affordable and easily accessible to the community cheaply.

The function of the Community Reading Parks (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat) is as a learning resource, information source and recreational-educational facility. As a learning resource, Community Reading Parks (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat) with the reading materials provided can provide services to the community to carry out reading and learning activities in order to support the creation of a lifelong learning society.

long life education. In this case, the community needs to continue to be nurtured and developed towards the formation of an information society or an intelligent society. The aim of this Community Reading Park (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat) is to:

1. develop people's interest and passion for reading
2. support the cultivation of a passion for reading
3. encourage the realization of a lifelong learning society (long life education)
4. create the quality and independence of a knowledgeable, skilled, cultured, and civilized society

From the description above, the manager of the Community Reading Parks (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat) plays a role as a motivator, able to encourage the community to be willing and able to improve their reading skills with their

creativity in providing services. (<http://fauziep.com/taman-bacaan-community-rintisan/>). By optimizing existing Community Reading Parks (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat) and establishing new Community Reading Parks (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat), UGM policy makes the UGM Library a “*window of the world*” can be realized. Making Indonesian people intelligent and able to improve their welfare.

IV. CONCLUSION

As a form of concern for the community, the "UGM Serves Library" program is very good for increasing the level of reading interest in the community which is considered to be still low. This activity involves mobilizing all librarians at UGM and becoming coordinators for librarians throughout Yogyakarta, to serve the community.

1. The "UGM Library Serves" program as a form of social responsibility to society
2. The "UGM Library Serves" program by establishing two activities, namely Inspiration Classes and Community Reading Parks (Taman Bacaan Masyarakat): Optimizing existing ones and creating new ones.
3. Forming an Inspiration Class, where librarians are asked to teach in Elementary Schools (roadshow) to inspire and raise insightful awareness about the importance of Science and Technology.
4. Optimizing existing TBMs (Community Reading Parks) and building TBMs in areas that do not yet have them, to stimulate and ground the Indonesian National Reading Movement.
5. Activities involve all libraries, professional organizations and communities who are concerned with empowering the community, in the Yogyakarta environment to synergize and integrate, working hand in hand into the community
6. UGM Library becomes *trendsetter* in community service for other libraries in Yogyakarta and throughout Indonesia.

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